

Body Weight and Linear Body Measurements of Three Nigerian Local Chicken Strains

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APA Citation and Referencing: Isaac, L. J., & Ekanem, I. E. (2025). Body Weight and Linear Body Measurements of Three Nigerian Local Chicken Strains. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 1(3), 251-254

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 20 Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Bodyweight Linear measurement Local chickens Strains</p>	<p>The body weight and linear body measurements of the Nigerian local chicken strains were studied with a view to assess their relationship and contribution to the growth of the birds. A total of three hundred (300) local chicken strains comprising one hundred (100) frizzle feathered (FF), one hundred (100) naked neck (NN) and one hundred (100) normal feathered (NM) birds each replicated ten (10) times with ten (10) birds per replicate, were used in the study. Data on body weight (BW) in grams (g) and linear body measurements (cm) – body length (BL), heart girth (HG), neck length (NL) and shank length (SL) – collected weekly for ten (10) weeks and analyzed in a completely randomized design (CRD) of SAS, (2001) statistical package. Significantly different means were separated using the Duncan multiple range test (DMRT). Results showed that there were significant variations in BW, BL, NL and SL, an indication that breed differences is implicated in the growth and development of chickens.</p>

1. Introduction

Breeders have tried to establish a relationship between body weight and some linear body measurements in order to speed up selection and improve breeding programs in animals (Ikeh and Okwesili, 2021; Muh. Akramullah et al., 2021; Negash, 2021), which provides critical information regarding the productivity and performance of the birds (Ikeh and Okwesili, 2021).

Body weight is significant for any selection and breeding program, feeding, vaccination, and drug dosage in animal production (Tyasi et al., 2020) and in ascertaining the growth rate of an animal and its price during marketing. Its relationship with other linear body measurements has been described to have important implications. Hence, the success of a breeding program relies on the ability to establish relationships that exist between identified traits (Tyasi et al., 2020). It is very important to consider the relationship between body weight and body measurement traits as this could be a useful selection criterion for improving body weight (Ikeh and Okwesili, 2021).

Body weight is important in that it helps in evaluation of growth performance, feed efficiency and the market price, and assessment of growth in livestock. However, other growth traits related to body morphometric are relevant factors considered by poultry breeders/farmers for assessment of growth in livestock, as they also serve as growth indicators (Hlokoe et al., 2022; Selala and Tyasi, 2022; Lamido et al., 2024), playing a pivotal role in routine farm management activities such as drug administration dosage, assessment of the amount of feed consumed, and response thereof to that feed (Haq et al. 2020; Rotimi et al. 2020; Hlokoe et al. 2022). Growth in animals could be evaluated from the component parts of the animal. This implies that improvements in the body measurements will invariably lead to a corresponding improvement in the body weight (Ikeh and Okwesili, 2021), as they make up the skeleton which determines the general shape of the body, which carries the body and is closely related to the muscles (Sadick et al., 2020).

Based on the fact that most linear measurements reflect primarily the length of the bones of animals, its relationship with body weight is important as this could be useful as a selection criterion to improve the body weight (Ikeh and Okwesili, 2021). Moreover, the knowledge of an animal's weight and weight changes is also key in determining responses to selection (Becker 2021; Faraz et al. 2021). This study was therefore carried out to assess the linear body measurements in different strains of the Nigerian local chickens.

2. Materials and Methods

Three hundred local chickens comprising of one hundred (100) Frizzle feathered (FR), one hundred (100) Naked neck (NN) and one hundred (100) Normal feathered (NM) strains sourced from local markets in Uyo, Uruan, Ibesikpo Asutan, Ibiono Ibom, Ikono and Ikot Ekpene Local Government Areas were used in this study. They were replicated ten (10) times with ten (10) birds in each replicate. They were kept in deep litter system with wood shaving litter material. Commercial growers mash and water were given *ad libitum*. The birds, aged between sixteen (16) to twenty – four (24) months, were kept for ten (10) weeks.

The study was conducted in the poultry unit of the Department of Animal Science, University of Uyo where birds were raised. Body weight and phenotypic (morphometric) traits (linear body measurements) were taken on the animals. The morphometric traits were: Body length (BL): measured from nasal opening with neck carefully stretched and along the back to the pygostyle. Heart girth (HG): measured by wrapping a tape rule around the breast under the wings. Neck length: Distance from the back of the head to the shoulder blade. Shank length (SL): Distance between the foot pad and hock joint. Data on body weight (g) and body measurements (cm) - heart girth, body length, neck length and shank length) were collected weekly and analyzed in a completely randomized design (CRD) of SAS (2001) statistical package, while Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to separate means that show significant differences.

3. Results and Discussion

The effect of strain on body weight and linear body traits of the investigated indigenous chicken strains is presented in Table 1. Genotype had significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on body weight, body length, neck length and shank length. The frizzle feathered (1041.24 g) and the naked neck (1065.21 g) strains were significantly higher in body weight than the normal feathered strain (973.42 g) even though they did not differ from each other. The frizzle feathered strain had a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher body length (19.34 cm) and shank length (6.84 cm) than the normal feathered strain with body length (18.18 cm) and shank length (6.37 cm). It showed no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in these parameters from the naked neck strain with body length (19.00 cm) and shank length (6.78 cm). The naked neck strain was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in neck length (12.12 cm) than the normal feathered strain (11.53 cm) but was not different from the frizzle feathered strain (11.77 cm) in this parameter. However, the heart girth showed no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference among the three strains.

The naked neck and frizzle feathered strains of chicken, with a body weight that did not show any significant difference amongst them, had higher body weights, which differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) from that of the normal feathered strain of chicken. This is in line with the reports of Udeh *et al.* (2011); Gwarza and Elkana (2017), that these strains perform differently, and Magothe *et al.* (2010), that the frizzle feather and naked neck genes allows for a better feed conversion on them which in turn may equally have accounted for the increased body weight as exhibited by them.

Body girth showed no differences in the strains, an indication that strain differences had no effect on body girth. This result differs from that of Udoh and Isaac (2014) where the naked neck cockerels had a higher body girth, while the normal feathered pullet had a higher body girth than the other strains.

The body length of the frizzle feathered local chicken was higher than the normal feathered but not different from naked neck strains. This is an indication that frizzles and naked neck genotypes enhance body development. The result is in line with that of Gwarza and Elkana (2017) where the broad helmeted guinea hens had a higher body length than the narrow-helmeted hens. Similarly, the cocks had a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher body length than the hens. The naked neck species equally had a longer body length than the frizzle and normal feathered species (Udoh and Isaac, 2014).

The neck length of the naked neck and the frizzle feathered strains were longer than that of the normal feathered. This agreed with Gwarza and Elkana (2017) who reported that the broad helmeted guinea cocks had a longer neck than the narrow-pointed guinea cocks. More so the guinea cocks had a higher neck length than the guinea hens, an indication of strain effect.

The naked neck and the frizzle feathered strains differed ($p < 0.05$) significantly in shank length from those with normal feathers, a pointer that there exist strain differences in the development of the component parts of the body of an animal. These results agreed with the fact that the naked neck strain had a higher shank length than the strain with frizzle and normal feathers and that naked neck cockerels had higher shank length than the cockerels of other strains (Udoh and Isaac, 2014).

The Naked neck strain exhibited a higher body weight over the normal and Frizzled-feathered strains which may be due to possessing gene for feather distribution (Naked neck gene) that is involved in reducing feather mass of 20–40%, thus improving heat dissipation through the naked area. This heat dissipation, leads to less depression of appetite and as such good growth especially at high temperatures. More so, producing fewer feathers makes available protein for other tissues like muscle to be synthesized (Singh *et al.*, 2001).

Table 2 shows the t-value, F-value and significant level of strain comparison between the Frizzle and the Normal Feathered chicken strains. Strain had an effect on body weight and body length in these two strains, with the Frizzle feathered strain having a higher body weight (1041.24 g) and body length (19.34 cm) values than the Normal feathered strain with body weight (973.42 g) and body length (18.82 cm). Other body parameters (heart girth; 28.54 cm for frizzle feathered There were no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in other body parameters (heart girth; 28.54 cm for frizzle feathered and 28.51 cm for normal feathered, neck length; 11.77 cm for frizzle feathered and 11.53 cm for normal feathered and shank length; 6.83 cm for frizzle feathered and 6.37 cm for normal feathered).

However, the t-value shows that the frizzle feathered strain differed significantly from those with normal feathers for body weight, heart girth and body length, but not in neck and shank lengths.

Comparing the frizzle and normal feathered strains showed the frizzle to have a higher body weight and body length than the normal. This is an indication of the fact that there is strain effect in the development of the two strains.

Strain comparison between Frizzle feather as well as the Naked Neck strains in local chicken is presented in Table 3 showing the t-value, F-value and the significant levels. Strain had a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on body weight with the naked neck (1065.21 g) having a higher body weight than the Frizzle feather (1041.24 g),

while the other body parameters (heart girth; 28.79 cm for naked neck and 28.54 cm for frizzle feathered, body length; 19.00 cm for naked neck and 19.34 cm for frizzle feathered and shank length; 6.78 cm for naked neck and 6.83 cm for frizzle feathered) did not show any significant differences. The t-values showed that the two strains differed with respect to body weight, heart girth,

neck and body lengths whereas shank length showed no difference. Similarly, comparing frizzle feathered and naked neck strains revealed naked neck to be better than the frizzle feathered in body weight.

The variations, in the F- and t- values, goes further to align with the fact that the different strains exhibit different growth patterns. The naked neck strain shows a significantly higher body weight (1065.21 g) just like body length (19.00 cm) than the body weight (973.42 g) and body length (18.82 cm) of the normal feathered strain (Table 4). Heart girth (28.79 cm), neck length (12.12 cm) and shank length (6.78 cm) for the naked neck strain were not different from the normal feathers (heart girth; 28.51 cm, neck length; 11.53 cm and shank length; 6.37 cm). The t-value showed that both strains differed from each other in heart girth, body weight and neck length, but not in body and shank lengths. The t-values for the three strains showed variations among linear body traits (parameters). It showed further that the strains exhibited varying and similar tendencies in the growth of the various body traits considered. This supports the fact that there exist strain differences in development of component parts of the body of the birds. Body weight and body linear measurements were significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced by the breed of the birds (Tyasi *et al.*, 2021), and according to Assan *et al.* (2025), morphometric traits showed slight differences between chicken breeds which indicates that different chicken breeds have different sizes and body weights. Variations in morphometric traits could provide valuable information for the design of genetic improvement and selection programs for chickens, which rely primarily on variations within and between breeds or populations (Shafiq *et al.*, 2022) and is an indication that traits could vary due to genotype (Tadelea *et al.*, 2023; Ade *et al.*, 2024).

4. Conclusion

There were variations in body weight and the linear body measurements of the different strains of the local Nigerian chickens. This is an indication of strain effect in the performance of these birds and thus should be considered as breeding plans are being designed.

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Appendix

Table 1: Strain effect on body weight and linear body traits

Traits	Frizzle feathered	Normal feathered	Naked Neck	SEM
Body weight (g)	1041.24 ± 13.94 ^a	973.42 ± 19.30 ^b	1065.21 ± 27.78 ^a	10.81
Heart girth (cm)	28.54 ± 0.29	28.51 ± 0.20	28.79 ± 0.24	0.14
Body length (cm)	19.34 ± 0.14 ^a	18.18 ± 0.06 ^b	19.00 ± 0.20 ^{ab}	0.09
Neck length (cm)	11.77 ± 0.14 ^{ab}	11.53 ± 0.18 ^b	12.12 ± 0.17 ^a	0.10
Shank length (cm)	6.84 ± 0.17 ^a	6.37 ± 0.11 ^b	6.78 ± 0.17 ^{ab}	0.09

^{abc} Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly (p<0.05) different from each other.

Table 2: Strain comparison between Frizzle and Normal Feathered chickens

Parameter	N	Frizzle Feathered	Normal Feathered	T	F	Sig.
Body Weight(g)	50	1041.24 ^a	973.42 ^b	1034.41*	3.05	0.10
Heart Girth(cm)	50	28.54	28.51	18.58*	0.60	0.45
Body Length(cm)	50	19.34 ^a	18.82 ^b	5.75*	7.30	0.02
Neck Length(cm)	50	11.77	11.53	0.57	0.20	0.66
Shank Length(cm)	50	6.83	6.37	3.01	0.98	0.34

^{abc} Means in the same row having different superscript are significantly (p<0.05) different from each other, N= sample size, F = calculated F-value, Sig = significance, T= calculated t-value.

Table 3: Strain comparison between Frizzle Feathered and Naked Neck chickens

Parameter	N	Frizzle Feathered	Naked Neck	T	F	Sig.
Body Weight(g)	50	1041.24 ^b	1065.21 ^a	1058.26*	10.85	0.04
Heart Girth(cm)	50	28.54	28.79	18.88*	0.32	0.58
Body Length(cm)	50	19.34	19.00	6.24*	1.70	0.21
Neck Length(cm)	50	11.77	12.12	6.43*	0.63	0.43
Shank Length(cm)	50	6.83	6.78	2.83	0.02	0.88

^{abc} Means in the same row having different superscript are significantly (p<0.05) different from each other, N= sample size, F = calculated F-value, Sig = significance, T= calculated t-value.

Table 4: Strain comparison between Normal Feathered and Naked Neck chickens

Parameter	N	Normal Feathered	Naked Neck	T	F	Sig.
Body Weight(g)	50	973.42 ^b	1065.21 ^a	1060.30*	3.51	0.05
Heart Girth(cm)	50	28.51	28.79	14.39*	0.02	0.90
Body Length(cm)	50	18.82 ^b	19.00 ^a	0.24	13.98	0.02
Neck Length(cm)	50	11.53	12.12	5.80*	0.04	0.84
Shank Length(cm)	50	6.37	6.78	1.10	1.43	0.25

^{abc} Means in the same row having different superscript are significantly (p<0.05) different from each other, N= sample size, F = calculated F-value, Sig = significance, t= calculated t-value.